

EFFECTIVE WAYS TO LEARN ENGLISH

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Annotation

The article is devoted to the consideration of various, in our opinion, effective ways of learning English. The publication discusses the possibility of using author's methods, which contribute to the rapid study of foreign languages, and in particular the English language.

Key words

English, learning English, ways of learning English, author's methods of learning English.

The modern pace of life, whether we like it or not, sets its own time frame, keeps us in the eternal "rhythm of the dance", the non-observance of which unsettles us. To date, the vast majority of people are engaged in the study of a foreign language. Each of them has its own purpose of study, some

- these are eternal business trips, for others - travel.

Every day people are more and more eager to learn a foreign language in a short time. For a period of time and first of all they are sent for help to various language learning organizations. But we decided to simplify the task and get acquainted with the most effective ways of learning a foreign language. Learning a foreign language (especially new words and expressions) is hard and painstaking work that requires constant cramming and spending a lot of time. Is it so? Is it really impossible to avoid these unpleasant moments for us? To answer exciting questions, we want to draw your attention to a rich list of modern techniques that help people around the world every day. The first technique that I want to introduce is the technique of Inna Maksimenko, the founder of author's English courses. She refers to her methodology as a strategy. So let's look at her strategies. Strategy 1. "Use the power of emotions." The author advises to associate English words with something important, positive for you, with something that concerns you. That is, when memorizing something new, we must first of all "pass it through ourselves." Namely, this will help us survive this or that language situation (for example, let's take the moment when we learn a topic, for example, on the topic "Travel"), if memorizing aimlessly, because there is a word "must", then it will be it is not at all easy to do, and if we imagine that this is OUR journey, then WE will make our task much easier. Thus, Inna Maksimenko advises: "Before remembering a word, think about how important and necessary it is for you. Would you like to use it further in your vocabulary?" Know how to weed out information you do not need in the future. Strategy 2. "Believe in your abilities." Do you have a good memory? Do you find it easy to memorize English words? Thoughts are material. Stop convincing yourself that languages are difficult for you or that this is not your thing. We do not notice this, but our brain absorbs information like a sponge, both positive (which was mentioned earlier) and negative. That is, telling yourself that you can't, you thereby program your brain to resist learning (by the way, this applies not only to

learning foreign languages, but also to any other activity). The main thing in this strategy is to believe in yourself, Maksimenko is sure. Strategy 3. "Remember forever." Many today are concerned about the question that "Will I forget what I have learned if I do not have the opportunity to reinforce knowledge? Can I postpone self-study and wait until the moment when the language is useful to me in practice? The answer to this question also largely depends on the beliefs and motivation of the person himself. Successful language learners usually believe in their ability to quickly recover knowledge. "When I have such a need, I will quickly remember everything that I need," they say. Our beliefs affect the brain's ability to store information. It is advised to set a time bar for what period of time knowledge can be restored. Strategy 4. "Remember the goal." It has been repeatedly proven by scientists that people who have a good reason for learning a language are able to master it much faster than others. That is why it is customary to set homework when studying at school - knowing that the learned new words will be useful in the next lesson, students, according to statistics, remember words better than those who were not given homework. Thus, motivation and purpose are fundamental in the effective study of a foreign language. Strategy 5. "Learn unconsciously." It is no secret that our unconscious learns new material much better and faster than the conscious. For example, when you drive a car, your attention is completely focused on the road, while the unconscious learns new words from the lyrics of the song playing in the radio. Try to read interesting books, stories more often, listen to audio materials, video materials and communicate with people in English. Then your consciousness will be busy with the plot, and the unconscious will be able to easily learn new words and expressions. And, perhaps, the most effective, in our opinion, Maksimenko's strategy is to "build" a new word into your experience. If we pay attention to a small child for whom everything is new, we will notice that when a child encounters a new word, he begins to notice it in a variety of situations, environments, and contexts. For example, when hearing the word "white" for the first time, the child begins to repeat it when he sees white snow, white paper, white sugar. And this is the key to correct, quick and easy memorization of a new word. In this strategy, attention is again drawn to the functions of our brain, which forms associations with various parts of previous experience, with what the child already knows well. In the contexts that the child uses when memorizing, the new word becomes more familiar and familiar. After all, now it remains only to remember sugar or snow. Inna Maksimenko advises using new words in a variety of situations - using it in retelling, practicing English with fellow students, with native speakers. Imagine yourself as that child. I would also like to introduce you to the step-by-step effective memorization of words and expressions from Sergey Grigorievich Khalipov (who is a polyglot who knows about 40 languages and easily memorizes new languages using his own methodology) Stage one. Always try to write down a new foreign word you hear using transcription (thus you compensate for the effort expended with the accuracy of articulation). To be convinced of this method, it is enough to look into any English phrase book, where the sound of foreign words will be written in Russian letters. You will immediately be convinced of the terrible distortion of the true sound of a foreign word, for example, the familiar word girl will be spelled out as "gel", and birth "bet" or "boef". When using such pronunciation options, you will not only not come close to English pronunciation, but you will not be understood at all by native speakers. Thus, transcription is our assistant in mastering the differences between the phonetic system of the language being studied and the system of the native language, in our case, the Russian

language. It is important, when recording the transcription of the word (expression) heard, to simultaneously repeat it aloud. So, let's imagine that we wrote a new word in the form of a transcription. We pass to the second stage. Second phase. It represents the construction of associations and visual images associated with the studied word, expression. For example, we present visually the same girl (thus we once again consolidate the word we heard). In the next third stage, we bring our pronunciation to a state of "comfort" (philologists call it "Articulatory Comfort"). This means that when learning a new phrase, we should not experience discomfort in pronunciation. At this stage, ideally, one should use authentic speech, that is, the speech of a native speaker (in turn, these are audio, video recordings, or, directly, the native speaker himself). At the fourth stage, it is advised to pronounce the phrase with acceleration, bringing it to the state of a tongue twister. Feel free to help yourself with gestures. The last fifth stage is the return to the usual pace of pronunciation. After the "patter" we will immediately notice the difference between the beginning of the consolidation and the current pronunciation of our new phrase. So, by using these not difficult steps according to the Khalipov method, we can easily master new words, expressions, sentences, texts, and later new foreign languages. We will not tire of reminding you of the endless list of tips for learning English. Going through the tips, one cannot ignore the creative exercises for effectively learning new words for us. a) Try to make up a story from the words/idioms/phrases you have learned. For example, today you learned new words on the topic "Traveling", such as boarding - landing, boarding card - boarding pass, passport control - passport control, to check in - register, hand luggage - hand luggage and similar words on this topic. After familiarizing yourself with the words on this topic, it goes without saying that you should compose a mini-text using these words. b) Make cards with the most difficult words to remember. This is done like this: we take two yellow square stickers, which we glue together, as a result we get a dense square sheet. On one side we write down the word, and draw a schematic association with this word. On the other side we write the translation. Why is yellow recommended? Because it is on the yellow color that our brain remembers better. c) Make a semantic accent or intonation accent. The semantic, in this case, refers to the Tatar word "divana", which translates as "fool", therefore, we can use the semantic accent by composing such an expression as "the fool fell off the sofa" - such a phrase in translation will help us lay down a new word "sofa" in our cerebral cortex. With an intonational accent, everything is much simpler: while memorizing a new one, we select already known, suitable words for the word and pronounce the resulting sentences out loud, focusing on the word we are studying.[2] d) Own story with illustration. We select two consonant words and put them in a kind of "our" story, do it in writing (while highlighting new words in italics or in various highlights), while for greater efficiency it is advised to also visually depict the story, or at least schematically, with some kind of picture, associated with the new word). WHY SHOULD THIS BE DONE ON A LETTER? Because according to numerous studies of scientists, it has been revealed that most people are visual. There are many techniques, methods and strategies that, like all people, are individual. The main thing today is to have a desire, the main thing is to want!

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